

SPECIAL ISSUE PAPER **OPEN ACCESS**

Decentralized Anomaly Detection Using Deep Feed-Forward Neural Networks

Christian Lübben¹ | Marc-Oliver Pahl^{1,2}¹School of Computation, Information and Technology, Technical University of Munich, Munich, Germany | ²IRISA, Chaire Cybersecurity for Critical National Infrastructures, IMT Atlantique, Rennes, France**Correspondence:** Christian Lübben (christian.luebben@tum.de)**Received:** 22 April 2024 | **Revised:** 26 July 2024 | **Accepted:** 19 October 2025**Funding:** This research was supported by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research under funding number 16KIS1221, “Proaktive Sicherheit durch Künstliche Intelligenz in automobilen und industriellen IT-Netzwerken” (SKINET), and Horizon Europe research and innovation project CyberSecDome under Grant Agreement No. 101120779.**Keywords:** anomaly detection | decentralized | device-specific | distributed | edge | federated learning | IoT | model aggregation | neural network | security

ABSTRACT

The Internet of Things (IoT) requires sophisticated security due to heterogeneity and resource constraints. Current anomaly detection (AD) approaches address none of these challenges. Local AD models can account for device heterogeneity. However, existing approaches cannot run on constrained devices. This paper implements decentralized local AD models. Each model processes data from only one device. Simplifying the prediction task results in lightweight AD models. They provide an opportunity to address the resource constraints of devices. With less need for processing power, IoT devices can perform AD on their own. The novel approach improves the optimization metrics of detection performance, latency, bandwidth usage, privacy, and model complexity. Further optimization using model aggregation speeds up the creation of AD models. The evaluation uses the publicly available UNSW-NB15 dataset. It shows that models can be simplified to run on IoT devices. Measurements with a local model on a Raspberry PI show only a slight increase in training and processing time compared with central remote processing on a significantly more powerful desktop PC. While the accuracy remains > 98%, the F1 score increases from 0.64 to 0.89 in the decentralized approach. The time for the creation of models is reduced by more than 90%.

1 | Introduction

Botnets like Mirai [1] demonstrate the impact of attacks on the expanding Internet of Things (IoT). The growth of the IoT has made it a lucrative target for attackers. The large number of devices to infect, and the acquisition of private user information attract attackers to constantly invent new attacks.

Intrusion detection systems (IDS) have proven to be an effective measure in securing computer networks. Heuristic approaches are increasingly being replaced by anomaly-based approaches

due to modern computer networks' complex and dynamic behavior, and the threat of zero-day vulnerabilities [2]. Even though anomaly-based approaches perform well, they still need to learn the benign behavior of a computer network. Network traffic modeling is a complex problem due to the large number of participants and patterns to be modeled. It requires high computing power and large data within the training process. A common IoT approach is collecting features on edge devices and sending them to a central processing instance that has the resources to process the data. This creation of a global model has several drawbacks that affect bandwidth usage, privacy,

Abbreviations: AD, anomaly detection; AE, autoencoder; FL, federated learning; IoT, Internet of Things; ML, machine learning; NN, neural network.

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2025 The Author(s). *International Journal of Network Management* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

and latency: Sending anomaly detection (AD) data reduces the network bandwidth available for operational purposes. Sending data over the network can raise privacy concerns. In addition, remote anomaly detection increases decision latency compared with local processing. One solution to these issues is local data processing. In the IoT domain, this solution must account for limited device resources. Available processing power and RAM limit the complexity of the applicable AD models, which reduces detection accuracy.

This work presents an approach to simplify the AD prediction task and enables the use of lightweight prediction models for IoT devices. It combines decentralized edge computing and local AD models into a modular approach. The local models allow individual retraining and replacement. Placing the local models on edge devices improves latency, model complexity, and detection performance.

This paper addresses the research question of how to do AD in a fully decentralized way by studying in detail:

- Creation of flexible AD models that allow individual retraining and simple addition of new devices
- Optimization toward constrained resources, low complexity, and high detection performance
- Enabling fast model bootstrapping and increasing detection performance

Edge devices have multiple definitions. This work defines them as devices with limited computational resources, including energy-constrained battery-powered devices. They are located at the outer edge of a network. Most characteristically, data are collected on these devices. Routers and access points typically do not fall into the definition of edge devices as they act as information relays. However, a minimum amount of processing power is required to perform AD. If routers are the first devices capable of performing AD tasks on the path from a data source to the network, AD services can also be placed there. By using lightweight models, the presented approach pushes the applicability of AD models toward the edge. Thus, the definition of decentralized in this paper is that data processing is pushed to the edge as much as technically possible and does not necessarily take place at the farthest node. AD-enabled devices can monitor a cluster of non-AD-enabled devices. This paper's evaluation uses a Raspberry PI as an exemplary device for executing AD tasks. The evaluation uses the publicly available UNSW-NB15 dataset [3]. This dataset provides labeled benign and anomalous data, including attacks from multiple devices. The model implementation uses autoencoders (AE) and deep feedforward neural networks (DFNN) for anomaly detection. This work extends the related work by applying a divide-and-conquer approach as presented in [4] to simplify the prediction task and create lightweight AD models.

The key contributions are as follows:

- A modular AD approach with local models
- Flexible retraining and addition of individual AD models

- Lightweight AD models meeting IoT resource constraints
- Significant improvement in detection performance
- Fast bootstrapping of AD models for new devices
- Selective FL-optimized local AD models
- An extensive evaluation of the novel approach

Section 2 presents the state-of-the-art. Section 3 introduces the approach and details the model creation. Section 4 compares the presented decentralized approach with a centralized one and highlights its advantages. Section 5 summarizes the results.

2 | Related Work

The related work on decentralized anomaly detection combines the topics of federated learning (FL), IoT traffic classification, and local modeling. The analysis of the related work reveals important IoT optimization goals: (1) Related work using federated learning highlights *bandwidth optimization*, *privacy*, and *latency* as optimization goals. A disadvantage of these works is the high model complexity. The approaches train global models, including information about the entire network. The resulting models contain information that is not relevant to each edge device. (2) Works in the area of IoT traffic classification add the creation of *lightweight* models to the list of optimization goals. They present solutions for latency reduction and lightweight model creation. They do not provide solutions for bandwidth optimization or privacy. All works in this category use global models and a centralized approach. (3) Works on local modeling provide several solutions for lightweight models and latency reduction. However, only [5] focuses on bandwidth reduction and privacy.

For all three topics, the following sections present relevant related works. They analyze whether the related works focus on (a) local detection and (b) enable decentralized detection on edge devices. They also analyze how the works address the challenges of bandwidth, latency, privacy, and lightweight models. Section 2.4 highlights the state-of-the-art in fulfilling the extracted optimization goals, and the contribution of the presented approach. Reference [6] provides a basic selection of IoT AD approaches.

2.1 | Decentralized Approaches

Like the proposed approach, decentralized approaches make use of the increasing computing power of edge devices. One main goal is decreasing bandwidth usage by transferring preprocessed intermediate data [7–11]. This allows the distribution of the prediction task and enables parallel data processing [10]. The transfer of intermediate data, such as model weights, provides increased privacy preservation [7, 9, 11]. However, reverse engineering the model weights could still reveal sensitive information.

Most works, still include centralized processing [7–9]. This limits model independence and availability over unreliable

network connections. Moving models to edge nodes enables local processing. This reduces prediction latency [8]. A problem with [8] is the focus on networks with similar AD targets. The IoT typically consists of heterogeneous devices [6]. Reference [9] combines federated learning with deep reinforcement learning (DRL) and distributes NN-layers to edge devices. References [10, 11] include a very similar approach to the proposed one. However, they train a distributed model of global traffic by incorporating federated learning. Compared with local models, this leads to unnecessary model complexity on edge devices. In this case, all models must learn the patterns of global traffic. Depending on the placement of edge devices, not all patterns may be relevant for a particular section of the network.

2.2 | Classification

The related approaches in the field of IoT AD can be divided into NN-based [12–18] and graph-based [19, 20] ones. The NN-based approaches mostly rely on deep learning (DL) with more than one hidden layer [12, 16, 18]. Meeting IoT constraints, the NN complexity is still limited, with hidden layers ranging from one [13, 14] to a maximum of three [12, 16]. More complex approaches use convolutional NN (CNN) [7] and ensemble methods [15]. The most common NN architectures for AD in the IoT are AE [16, 17] and deep neural networks (DNN) [12, 18]. All works have in common that they are neither local nor decentralized. Because they require all input data from the observed devices, their central placement does not provide solutions for bandwidth optimization or privacy. The centralized approach achieves latency reduction through faster processing of the prediction task [13, 15, 18]. Lightweight solutions use lightweight libraries [12] or reduce hidden layers [13, 14], features [16], or rules [20].

2.3 | Local Model Creation

Local models are used for device identification [21–23], anomaly detection [5, 24, 25], and traffic modeling [26, 27]. Their focus on the device level allows the creation of lightweight models due to fewer characteristics to learn [5]. Device identification is typically done using random forests (RF) [21–23]. Local anomaly detection uses either NN in the form of gated recurrent units (GRU) [5] or clustering (FIS, BIRCH) [24, 25]. Traffic models rely on rule-based approaches [26, 27] or graphs [28]. To address the challenges of privacy and bandwidth, [5] incorporates a federated learning approach. It is the only work that takes bandwidth and privacy into account. Lightweight approaches use either clustering [24, 25], trees [23], or rules [26]. Decentralized approaches place dedicated security gateways in the network [5, 23] or place the anomaly detection directly on the device running the service to be modeled [24]. This eliminates the need to transmit data across the entire network and prevents visibility of data transmission and eavesdropping by remote nodes. While [23] uses the federated approach to create device fingerprints locally and process them in the cloud, [5, 24] use federated learning to exchange AD information with other IoT sites. Although several works focus on low latency [5, 23–26], no general strategy can be derived.

2.4 | Summary

Table 1 summarizes the findings. For each paper, it shows the year of publication, the focus on local or decentralized processing, the achievement of optimization goals, and the ML approach used.

To reduce bandwidth usage, related works propose the placement of data processing close to the affected device [5, 23, 24]. This work goes one step further and places even the data processing on the monitored device. This minimizes data transmission to its optimum zero because no data need to be transmitted for AD purposes. Related works reduce latency either by optimizing transmission or data processing. Reducing the distance between the model and the target device and thus the round trip time of the AD information [8] decreases transmission latency. Optimizing the classification process accelerates data processing [13, 15, 18]. The proposed approach implements both. By using lightweight models, it enables fast processing on constrained hardware while keeping local latency low. Placing processing near or on the device being modeled minimizes or eliminates transmission latency. Approaches for optimizing privacy are the transmission of intermediate results [7, 9] or processing data on [24], or near [5, 10] the monitored device. The proposed approach avoids all data transfers by placing AD on the monitored node. Thus, no privacy-sensitive information leaves the originating device.

Approaches to create lightweight NN are the limitations of layers [13, 14] and features [16]. The proposed approach promotes the use of lightweight models by simplifying the prediction task. Because only local features need to be learned, models can have a smaller capacity and, thus, fewer neurons and layers.

3 | Decentralized Local Anomaly Detection

Decentralized local anomaly detection consists of two main building blocks: decentralized AD and local AD models. The first part of this section introduces both building blocks with their goals and challenges. After explaining the building blocks, combining the two exploits the strengths of each idea. Because the approach operates in a decentralized manner, the placement of the components is crucial. The chosen placement is based on solving the optimization goals. The following sections introduce the proposed approach for decentralized local AD. They focus on data preprocessing, model creation, training, inclusion of new models, and security.

3.1 | Decentralized Anomaly Detection

Decentralized AD relies on decentralized data processing. Instead of processing data on a single centralized node, the processing is distributed across multiple nodes within the network. The resulting load-balancing capability reduces the hardware requirements for a single node as the amount of AD data to process is shared. This is a key design decision for data processing in resource-constrained environments. The critical task of placing the decentralized AD nodes and defining the part of the network to monitor is discussed in

TABLE 1 | Related work.

Work	Year	Local	Decentralized	Optimization goals				Approach
				Lightweight	Bandwidth	Privacy	Latency	
Li [7]	2018	X	pT ^a	X	✓	✓	X	CNN
Luo [8]	2018	✓	D ^b	✓	✓	X	✓	AE
Ren [9]	2019	✓	D ^b , pT ^a	X	✓	✓	✓	DRL
Schneible [10]	2017	X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	AE
Rahman [11]	2020	X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	FFNN
Thamilarasu [12]	2019	X	X	✓	X	X	X	DNN
Kim [13]	2018	X	X	✓	X	X	✓	SNN
Hanif [14]	2019	X	X	✓	X	X	X	SNN
Moustafa [15]	2019	X	X	X	X	X	✓	ADB
Al-Hawawreh [16]	2018	X	X	✓	X	X	X	AE
Telikani [17]	2019	X	X	X	X	X	X	AE
Rezvy [18]	2019	X	X	X	X	X	✓	DNN
Koroniotis [19]	2018	X	X	X	X	X	X	DT
Lanoe [20]	2018	X	X	✓	X	X	X	Graph
Meidan [21]	2017	✓	X	X	X	X	X	Multiple
Sivanathan [22]	2019	✓	X	X	X	X	X	RF
Miettinen [23]	2017	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	RF
Nguyen [5]	2018	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	GRU
Pahl [24]	2018	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	BIRCH
Hafeez [25]	2018	✓	X	✓	X	X	✓	FIS
Hamza [26]	2019	✓	X	X	X	X	✓	Rules
DeMarinis [27]	2017	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	Rules
Spathoulas [28]	2019	✓	X	X	X	X	X	Graph

Note: Implemented ✓: Yes; X: No.

^aPartly training.

^bDetection.

Section 3.3. Decentralized anomaly detection also presents system design challenges. The distribution of the monitoring data must ensure that meaningful models can be built. This means that the parts of the network to be monitored must be fixed, and the assignment of a monitored device to an AD model must be fixed. Synchronizing the results of multiple AD nodes is another challenge. In addition, assigning specific portions of the monitoring data results in less data to train. On the one hand, this reduces the complexity of the prediction task as fewer characteristics are included. On the other hand, it may result in incomplete training data that only represents some benign states of the network.

3.2 | Local Anomaly Detection

Local models shift AD from a global network view to a local one. This results in multiple local AD models instead of one

global network model. Device subdivision reduces the amount of data processed during training and detection. A model only needs to learn what is relevant to the observed devices. With fewer features to learn, it is expected that AD models can be simpler and lighter. This reduces the hardware requirements for processing. The assignment to a single device or group of devices leads to the independence of AD models. Thus, AD models can be distributed to available devices in the network and process data in parallel. This allows the combination with decentralized AD. The local models also solve the challenge of selecting meaningful data for decentralized AD models. Model independence also allows for retraining and replacement at any time without affecting AD on other devices. Any AD failure is limited to the affected device. Model (re)training can also be done in parallel. A challenge for local AD is detecting attacks that affect multiple local models. Because all models are independent, such attacks must be detected at a higher level that can combine the AD results of multiple local

models. Similar to decentralized AD, training data reduction is a challenge. This challenge also remains for the combination of both approaches.

3.3 | Placement

Placement is the essential design choice to address bandwidth utilization, latency, and privacy challenges. The independence of local models allows placement in any part of the network that can observe a target device's traffic. The placement of AD components can be inside or outside the relevant network. External placement can be in the cloud. In this case, all monitored traffic must be routed there. Internal placement often uses strategic points that can monitor the traffic of all devices [5, 23]. This work uses the approach of [24], which places the AD directly on the monitored device. This ensures that there is no unnecessary data transfer. All data are processed directly at the source. If placement on the observed device is impossible, [29] provides an automated service placement algorithm. The optimization goal is to minimize network traffic usage. For this purpose, the algorithm monitors the exchanged network traffic and considers the migration costs. It periodically evaluates the observed state and computes an optimal placement. Concerning unstable connections within the IoT, this placement also increases the availability of the AD by requiring fewer or no connections to pass through.

3.4 | Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing includes all the steps before a model can process the data. For the proposed approach, there are three main steps. (1) Feature engineering prepares all features to be compatible with the AD model. (2) Feature selection selects the features to be processed. (3) Data selection assigns the input data to the local AD models. The following sections describe all three steps in detail.

3.4.1 | Feature Engineering

Feature engineering begins with feature transformation. Because the applied NN can only process numerical data, all categorical data must be transformed. The proposed approach uses an embedding to translate the categorical values. The relationship between the embedding and the categorical value is stored in a dictionary to allow for the back conversion. IP addresses are converted to their decimal representation. Finally, all values are normalized to a range between zero and one using a min-max scaler. This mitigates the varying magnitudes of the features and aims to increase the accuracy of the model.

3.4.2 | Feature Selection

Because the proposed approach uses local models, manual selection or the use of domain knowledge does not scale with the growing number of different devices. Therefore, the feature selection is automated. A challenge is that the important features of the prediction model might vary between the different devices. As a solution to this challenge, the proposed approach adapts the

approach for automated feature selection in IoT AD presented in [16]. Instead of selecting individual features, it assigns an importance to each feature. This guarantees no loss of information due to dropped features. The approach satisfies the requirement of automated and dataset-independent feature selection by not using dataset-specific external knowledge. The implementation uses an AE to initialize the weights of a DFFNN. After an initial training phase with the AE, it loads the weights into the DFFNN and continues training. The training of the DFFNN uses labeled data. During training, the data are assumed to be purely benign. Thus, the label for all training data is zero.

3.4.3 | Data Selection

If the approach is running natively on the device being monitored, data selection is straightforward. In this case, the AD takes all inbound and outbound traffic for analysis. More difficult is the case of a partially decentralized scenario. If an edge device is unable to host the on-device AD itself, it can be placed on an external device. This can be the next hop of the network traffic. In this case, the device running the AD must select the information for each device model it hosts. If the device is responsible for only one monitored device, the selection is still trivial, as it simply takes all the transmitted traffic and analyzes it. If the device is responsible for multiple devices, it must feed multiple predictors with the correct data. In this case, an approach similar to the divide-and-conquer approach of [4] is taken. Traffic is split based on source and destination devices. For each device, the split creates one box. This results in n boxes, where n is the number of different devices. A box contains all incoming and outgoing traffic from that device. If the source and destination devices are on the monitored network, a packet is assigned to two boxes. For each box, a local model is trained on the corresponding data. This results in n independent local AD models. Even though in this case no on-device processing takes place, the task is still pushed toward the edge as much as possible. The optimization goals are still satisfied toward the higher network layers.

3.5 | Model Creation

This section presents the creation of lightweight models that allow processing on constrained resources. It starts with the presentation of the architecture of the used NN, which shows the lightweight design choices. This is followed by the presentation of the training steps. The next part presents the challenges of training local AD models. Finally, a solution to these challenges using federated learning and model aggregation is presented.

3.5.1 | Model Architecture

The proposed model is a fully connected DFFNN. The number of neurons and layers is adapted from the related work analysis. The most commonly used architecture is an AE [8, 10, 16, 17]. Two of them already implement lightweight models [8, 16]. Further analysis shows that the lightweight approaches keep the number of hidden layers below three. Therefore, the proposed DFFNN adapts this and uses three hidden layers. Because the

FIGURE 1 | Neural network architecture.

feature selection is already adapted from [16], the lightweight classification stage is taken as the basis for the proposed DFFNN. Figure 1 shows the architecture of the AE for the first training stage. It consists of an encoder and a decoder stage. The encoder stage compresses the input to hidden layer two. From the code in layer two, the decoder stage reconstructs the input and maps the reconstruction to the output layer. After initial training, the weights of this AE are transferred to the second model. The DFFNN looks similar to the AE up to the output layer. It just adds an additional layer with one neuron to the output layer of the AE. This layer is used as a binary output for the supervised second learning stage. Section 4.7 details the model parameters.

3.5.2 | Training

The training consists of two phases. The first unsupervised phase trains the AE. It takes all features of the dataset as input. Through compression and decompression, the AE calculates an output for all features. This output is compared with the input and the prediction error is calculated based on the mean squared error loss function. During training, the model weights are adjusted to minimize this error. The final weights are stored to be used as initial weights for the DFFNN.

The second state initializes the DFFNN with the weights from the first training stage. It uses supervised learning to train the DFFNN. It takes the same 47 input features as the first stage. The output is a single value. This value is compared with the binary dataset label of anomaly or benign. Again, the mean squared error function is used to calculate the loss. Each training iteration adjusts the weights to minimize the loss.

Model retraining can be initiated at any time. First, the weights of the current model must be loaded. Then retraining follows

the same steps as regular training with new data. When retraining is complete, the current model must be replaced with the new model. To allow forensics of past events, the replaced model should be saved.

3.5.3 | Challenges

Training with fewer data can result in incomplete data sets that do not contain all or sufficient training states, as Sections 3.1 and 3.2 present. One possible solution is to use federated learning, which combines information from multiple learners. Traditionally, all models are simply merged by aggregating their weights. A common aggregation function is the federated average (fed-avg). This function comes with several drawbacks. Not all information from the entire network is relevant to each part of the network. This is also the main idea behind the development of local models in this paper. To solve this information conflict, the successor of the NOMS 2023 paper [30] introduces the idea of selective federated learning [31]. It presents a solution for combining local models with federated learning. It introduces a similarity measure that selects only similar models for aggregation. Within the paper, this is used for fast bootstrapping, which is presented in the next section, which discusses the inclusion of new devices. A new application is the use of similarity-based FL for existing models. The goal is to augment the models by aggregating them with similar models. Although reducing bandwidth usage is a goal, the use of federated learning introduces some traffic. However, because only model weights are transmitted, the introduced overhead is limited. For one model, it is about 4.8 kB for 117 node NNs. The selected models are aggregated with the local model to incorporate external information. The federated part of this approach mitigates the impact of less and potentially incomplete learning data. The built-in model

similarity analysis preserves the idea of local training by selecting only relevant aggregation information.

3.6 | Adding New Devices

Adding new network devices to the AD requires a new model. The setup follows the steps suggested in Section 3.5.2. The approach scales as well as the decentralized approaches in [5, 24]. Their advantage is that no retraining of a global model is necessary to include the new device. A new dedicated model is spawned, and training is done in parallel to the already running AD on other devices.

One challenge in this process is establishing communication with existing devices. Because communication with the new device is not part of their model, it is likely that false positives will be generated. A mitigation strategy is to compare these false positives with the results of the new device model. If they are anomalous only in the existing model, retraining is triggered. Another challenge is the bootstrapping time until a new model is available. Although training is accelerated with lightweight local models, training times can still take up to several hours. As a mitigation, the successor of the NOMS 2023 paper [30] presents a fast bootstrapping algorithm that reduces the model initialization time [31]. The approach relies on model aggregation. To avoid including unnecessary information, a similarity analysis is performed to select only models that fit the new device. To enable fast bootstrapping, a central server must collect all models from devices in the network. These models are then sent to the new device. The models contain no information about their origin, so no information leakage or traceability is possible. These models are then run on a training dataset on the new device. All models with low loss are selected for model aggregation. Once created, the model can be applied and retrained in the background. Or it can simply be used until the model created by traditional training is complete. The final model is federated back to the central server.

3.7 | Security

Because security is the overall goal of performing AD, the presented approach itself is analyzed from a security perspective. The analysis focuses on the main security goals of integrity, confidentiality, and availability. In terms of integrity, the approach minimizes the attack surface for person-in-the-middle attacks that can inject or modify data. Because the data are processed locally, there is no or only local transmission. For the optimizations using FL, adversarial attacks are a possible scenario. These are mitigated by local similarity analysis. It provides injection resistance. A mismatching model will not be selected because its loss on the local dataset is too high. In terms of confidentiality, it is advantageous that transmissions are reduced to a minimum. Thus, interception of AD data is not possible. There is also no data exposure to other hosts. For federated optimizations, only the necessary model transfers take place. Because only models are shared with the central server, no privacy-relevant information, such as raw data, is exposed to the central server or other devices. The optimizations also provide privacy to the edge, because only models with a generic ID are shared with the edge

node. No other knowledge about the model sources is shared. Even if reverse engineering attacks are successful, no device associated with a particular model is known. Thus, no privacy-related information is exposed by the central server. The decentralized approach increases availability. Unlike centralized approaches, there is no single point of failure. The system generally remains operational even if one or more AD nodes fail. In addition, there is no high-value target containing sensitive data from multiple devices. For optimizations, the model server remains a special target. If the server goes down, the optimizations will not work. Because they are only optimizations, the AD remains functional. There is also no data exposure if the central node is hacked because it only contains a repository of models with generic IDs.

4 | Evaluation

An extensive evaluation is needed to thoroughly assess all the contributions of the new approach. It has to address all optimization goals as well as the performance in detection and runtime. To accomplish this, the evaluation initially identifies its targets and presents the corresponding experiments. Within the experiments, the evaluation compares the decentralized local approach with a centralized global model approach. It continues with explaining the metrics and the constrained *PI* and regular *PC* evaluation environments in detail. In the next step, it presents the dataset to be used within the experiments. The final sections of the evaluation preparation present the dataset-specific adaptations of the proposed approach regarding data preprocessing and model parameters. The last section presents the results and answers the questions defined in the evaluation targets.

Key findings of the evaluation are that the local approach outperforms the centralized one. Both approaches have a high accuracy of over 98% and differ by only 1%. The local approach has a significant advantage over the centralized approach in terms of F1 score, outperforming it by 25%. This advantage is mainly due to a twice-as-high anomaly detection rate. The complexity evaluation shows that lightweight models can be created without any loss in performance. Only the proposed approach maintains detection performance while reducing model complexity. In terms of training data, the local approach reduces the required amount by 30% compared with the centralized approach. The measurements on constrained hardware demonstrate the applicability of the approach in resource-constrained environments. The results show a difference of only 30% in data processing time and 20% in training time on hardware that is 10 times slower. Even if the models are not distributed, the ability of parallel processing local models can reduce training times. Within the evaluation environment, the training times are reduced by up to 80% on unconstrained hardware. The presented fast bootstrapping provides models with good detection performance while reducing the model initialization times by up to 97%.

4.1 | Experiments

This section derives the evaluation targets from the IoT optimization goals of Section 2.4 and presents the required experiments.

For the latency and lightweight models, multiple targets are defined, resulting in multiple experiments. EX1–EX4 aim to evaluate the use of lightweight models and determine whether their use leads to valid results. EX5 evaluates the latency of the proposed approach. EX6 and EX7 aim to evaluate the federated extensions to the local AD.

4.1.1 | EX1: Similar Parameters

For the decentralized approach to be useful, the detection performance must not be significantly worse than that of the centralized solution. Therefore, one evaluation target is *Model Performance*, answering the question: How does the decentralized approach compare to the centralized approach? The experiment compares the centralized and decentralized approaches with similar parameters. The model parameters are the default parameters presented in Section 4.7. Based on these parameters, one global and 43 local models are trained. The resulting models are then evaluated on an identical evaluation dataset. While the global model produces a single output, the outputs of the decentralized local models must be computed together. The results log TP, FP, FN, and TN as the basis for calculating the detection performance metrics.

4.1.2 | EX2 Model Complexity Variation

When evaluating the ability to reduce the complexity of detection models, the second objective is *Model Complexity Reduction*. EX2 answers the two questions: How does complexity reduction affect model performance for the local and global approaches? How does complexity affect training and processing times? It creates shallow models with one hidden layer for global and local models. The number of neurons in the hidden layer is 10. The resulting models are trained and evaluated on similar data. Again, the results of the decentralized models are computed together. The results include detection performance metrics and training time.

4.1.3 | EX3: Training Data Variation

The third target evaluates the *Data Requirement* of the global and local approaches by answering the question: What is the training data requirement of both approaches to achieve their final performance? In this context, the experiment successively increases the amount of data during the training for both approaches. It starts with 10% of the available training data and increases by 10% in each step. The results log detection performance metrics and training time.

4.1.4 | EX4: Constrained Training

The fourth target evaluates the overall goal of enabling AD on constrained resources. It measures the *Training Time* to answer the question: How does the training time compare between the two approaches and on constrained versus powerful hardware? In contrast to the previous experiments using only the PC environment, this experiment involves the constrained PI

environment. It logs the training times of AD models with an increasing number of training samples. Similar to EX3, it starts with 10% of the available training data and increases by 10% in each step. This approach also provides insight into scalability with increasing training data. The global model is trained on the PC environment. For the decentralized approach, one local model is trained on the Pi environment. Training in a constrained environment is intended to provide an upper bound for training local models. Therefore, the device with the largest number of training samples is selected. This ensures that the training of all other devices takes less time.

4.1.5 | EX5: Latency Comparison

The latency measurements assess the network-introduced latency of the centralized approach in comparison to the constrained-hardware-caused processing latency. The evaluation seeks to address the question of: How is the prediction latency, including introduced latency by slower hardware? The local processing latency for the global model is measured in the PC environment. The local model's processing latency is measured in the PI environment. Similar to EX4, the local model with the largest number of samples is selected to get an upper bound on the processing time. The results log the processing time for all evaluation samples of the selected device. The global approach must process all data from the first occurrence of the selected device to the last packet. All samples from other devices that fall within this period must also be processed, as they are part of the observed network traffic. The transmission latency evaluation is performed on a theoretical basis. No further measurements are taken, but the transmission capacity specifications are used to make a worst-case assessment of the minimum performance gain possible. The calculations are based on the theoretical maximums of network transmission for the supported standards of the PI environment.

4.1.6 | EX6: Federated Augmentation

EX 6 evaluates the models that are augmented by the use of selective FL. It answers the question: Can inclusion of selective federated knowledge improve the detection performance? During the experiment, a set of local models is augmented with the selective FL approach introduced in Section 3.5.3. For both the augmented and the original set of models, the model performance metrics are logged while processing the same evaluation dataset. The results log TP, FP, FN, and TN.

4.1.7 | EX7: Federated Bootstrapping

EX 7 evaluates the fast bootstrapping algorithm presented in Section 3.6. To evaluate the overall goal of reducing bootstrapping times, they need to be measured and compared, especially on low-resource hardware. This answers the question: Can bootstrapping be accelerated? Finally, the detection performance of fully aggregated models has to be evaluated to answer the question: Is complete aggregation a valid mechanism of model bootstrapping? To do this, it uses the fast similarity-based bootstrapping algorithm to create a new device model. In the

next step, it trains a model using the original approach presented in Section 3.5.2. For both approaches, it logs the time until the model is available. When both models are available, the corresponding evaluation dataset is used to compute the detection performance metrics. The results log TP, FP, FN, and TN. All measurements are made in the PI environment.

4.2 | Solved Optimization Goals

In contrast to latency and lightweight models, the bandwidth usage and privacy optimization goals have already been solved by design and do not require any further measurements. For them, this section details why no measurements are needed.

4.2.1 | Bandwidth Usage

As Section 3.3 presents, the AD is placed directly on the monitored device. Thus, there is no overhead in bandwidth usage. Therefore, it can be concluded that the bandwidth usage is optimal. Although a comparison with a centralized environment would be possible, it is omitted because it is highly dependent on the implementation of the centralized solution. If the AD is placed on a central network node that is used by all entities on the network, no additional traffic needs to be routed to the AD. The only overhead in this case would be the transmission of the results to the end node, which can be very small. Another extreme would be to transfer the raw data to a dedicated AD node. This would increase the overhead by at least 100% if no compression is used.

4.2.2 | Privacy

Privacy is also addressed by the on-device placement of AD models. This ensures that no data leaves the device. In particular, no raw data containing sensitive information is transmitted across the network. This ensures that no information is exposed to nodes that are not part of a communication anyway.

4.3 | Metrics

The evaluation metrics are derived from the evaluation targets. They must express the information needed to answer the questions. Because performance is important for several questions, the calculated metrics are presented in the next section. This is followed by a section that presents the IoT-specific metrics.

4.3.1 | Performance

The performance metrics are divided into two categories: detection performance and runtime performance. While the first group evaluates the correctness of the results, the second group evaluates the time until the result is available.

4.3.1.1 | Detection Performance. The metrics for the evaluation of the detection performance are in line with the usual metrics for the evaluation of ML approaches. The accuracy (1)

indicates the number of correctly labeled anomalies with respect to all samples. It allows a basic evaluation of the prediction quality. In scenarios with unbalanced data sets, which are common in anomaly detection scenarios, the results have to be considered with caution. A predictor may be biased toward the majority class. If there are only a few anomalies (true positive [TP]) in the dataset, the accuracy would still be high even if none of them are detected. A solution to this problem is to use precision (2) and recall (3). A metric that relies on both is the F1 score (4). It gives the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It is valuable for unbalanced data sets because it is sensitive to false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN).

$$\text{Accuracy} = (\text{TP} + \text{TN}) / (\text{TP} + \text{FP} + \text{FN} + \text{TN}), \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Precision} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FP}), \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FN}), \quad (3)$$

$$\text{F1} = 2 * (\text{Recall} * \text{Precision}) / (\text{Recall} + \text{Precision}). \quad (4)$$

4.3.1.2 | Runtime Performance. Runtime performance analyzes the duration of several steps within the AD. Training time measures the time it takes to fully train a new model. Processing time measures the time it takes a sample or batch of samples to be processed by a model. Data transmission time measures the time it takes to transfer required data to another node and back if necessary.

4.3.2 | IoT-Specific

Because bandwidth usage is already at its optimum, complexity is the only IoT-specific metric required during the evaluation. The evaluation uses several parameters to determine the complexity of models. Measurements show that an increase, especially in layers, leads to an increase in training and execution times [32]. Because the IoT provides only limited computing resources, the complexity should be low. During training, the amount of required data samples is also considered as part of the complexity. A lower number of required samples that leads to maximum detection performance indicates a simplification of the prediction task and results in lower training times.

4.4 | Environment

Measurements are taken in two different environments. All unconstrained resource measurements are performed on a desktop PC (PC) with 64 GB of RAM, an AMD Ryzen 9 3900X 12-core processor with a TDP of 105 W, and no GPU acceleration. All resource-constrained measurements are performed on a Raspberry Pi 3 Model B Plus Rev 1.3 (PI) with 4 cores and 1 GiB of RAM. Using a Raspberry Pi Zero 2 W would be a better choice in terms of power consumption. However, it is based on the same Broadcom BCM2837 chip as the Pi 3B. Expected differences in training and processing times are limited, as the performance of the Pi Zero is about 80% of the PI. The expected power consumption drops from a maximum of 7 W (PI) to a maximum of 3 W (Zero 2 W). Because this work does not aim at an exact measurement of the power consumption, the

Zero 2W is not used. Raspberry Pico or ESP32 consume even less power but require special prediction models due to their extremely low resources. (Pico: CPU 133 MHz, RAM 264 KB; ESP32: CPU 240 MHz, RAM 520 KB). This lacks comparability with the centralized solution. The software stack is Debian 11 and Python 3.9.2.

4.5 | Dataset

The dataset used for evaluation significantly impacts the representativeness of the measurement results. Therefore, it is necessary to have a dataset that contains traffic patterns and anomalies, including representative attacks. In addition, the dataset used for evaluation must be labeled. The majority of related works use their own datasets. While these datasets can accommodate individual requirements, the results generated lack comparability. Public datasets address the issue of comparability. There are several public datasets that at least partially meet these requirements. Two datasets commonly used in related work are the KDD99 [10, 17] and NSL-KDD [11, 13, 15–17] datasets. These datasets satisfy the requirement for a labeled test set of network traffic. Because both sets are based on the Darpa98 dataset, which was recorded in a simulated environment in 1998, they do not meet the second requirement. The traffic is no longer representative, as many new techniques have been introduced since then. In addition, the attacks included do not cover current threats. Therefore, more recent datasets are required. A third dataset commonly used in related works is the UNSW NB15 Dataset. It was recorded in 2015 and is a suitable candidate for use in this work. It is a labeled dataset and contains more recent network traffic, including more recent attack types. However, the dataset was recorded in an artificial environment, which may limit its applicability to real-world scenarios. This limitation is difficult to overcome, as all parameters, including traffic-generating services, must be controlled during dataset generation to ensure reliable labeling of each sample as malicious or benign. Because several related works have already used the UNSW-NB15 dataset [14–16, 19], this work adapts it. The dataset is publicly available at [33]. The evaluation uses the file *UNSW-NB15_1.csv* consisting of 700,000 samples. The time period covered is 7h, 53 min, and 48s, recorded on Thu Jan 22, 2015. The details of all 47 features and two labels are given in [3]. The next section describes the preprocessing applied to the UNSW-NB15 dataset.

4.6 | Data Preprocessing

The data preprocessing is divided into three steps as presented in Section 3.4. Feature engineering makes all features compatible with the NN model. This mainly consists of converting categorical features into numerical features. The second step is to select and weight the features. The third step organizes the data for local training.

4.6.1 | Feature Engineering

Feature engineering converts all categorical features. In the case of the UNSW-NB15 dataset, these are *state*, *protocol*, and

service. All three are replaced with a numeric embedding. The IP addresses are converted to their decimal representation. A byte-wise representation is omitted to avoid further increasing the number of input features. The decimal representation is also chosen to preserve the topological information. The addresses of a subnet are also close to each other in the decimal representation. An NN can thus learn to identify malicious IP address ranges. In the case of multiple benign subnets with distant IPs, this approach is limited. The train–test split is 80% and 20%. The training set contains 562,045 samples. The 20% testset sums up to a total of 279,645 samples. All experiments apply the same testset to generate the performance metrics. This ensures that the results are comparable. It fixes the number and types of anomalies to be detected as well as the benign data for both approaches. The preprocessing ensures that each local model trains on 80% of the device data. This ensures comparability of the models as they all use the same proportion of available training data. The test set consists of a merge over the remaining 20% of all boxes, resulting in 279,645 samples. It exceeds the expected 137,955 samples due to redundant entries.

4.6.2 | Feature Selection

As proposed in Section 3.4, the feature selection is adapted from [16]. The goal is to have an automated solution for feature selection because manual intervention is not possible with large amounts of data. In addition, it is not easy to decide from the beginning which features are valuable and which are not. Automation has to take into account that the selection of features is dataset-specific. Therefore, the proposed approach relies on automated feature weighting. The weighting ensures that all features are checked for relevance. It is encoded directly in the AE. The feature weights are transferred to the DFFNN via the weights of the AE. An evaluation of the adapted approach can be found in [16].

4.6.3 | Data Selection

The anomaly detection of the decentralized approach is local. In a native implementation, each device analyzes and models its own traffic as described in Section 3. This includes all incoming and outgoing packets. The UNSW-NB15 dataset combines all traffic captures into one file. This requires an additional step before preprocessing. The traffic split separates the global traffic into device-specific traffic, similar to the strategy proposed in Section 3.4. Figure 2 visualizes the IP-based traffic separation for the selected file of the UNSW-NB15 dataset. The left side visualizes the total traffic, which is split on the right side based on each individual IP address. The traffic split creates 43 boxes that are input to the model training. Thus, 43 individual device models are trained. Each model is associated with an IP address. A box contains traffic with that IP as either a source or destination. Because each device has one IP address, each box represents a device.

4.7 | Model Parameters

The model parameters are mainly adapted from [16] as they achieve good results when processing the UNSW-NB15

dataset. Layer-wise, the proposed DFFNN follows the architecture of three hidden layers. The neuron distribution of the hidden layers is 10–3–10. The initial training for weight initialization implements a regular AE with 47 input and output neurons. The supervised stage adapts the output layer to one neuron indicating the output as malicious or benign. The neurons use the *tanh* activation function. The output neuron also uses the *Sigmoid* function to scale the output value to the range between zero and one. The training uses a batch size of 1 within 100 epochs with a learning rate of 0.002. The optimizer uses gradient descent with a momentum of 0.4 and a weight decay of $1e-6$. The mean squared error is used as the loss function.

4.8 | Results

The following sections present the results of all experiments and answer the questions from Section 4.1. Each section belongs to one experiment.

4.8.1 | Model Performance

Table 2 contains the performance metrics results of EX1. The better values are printed in bold. The accuracy for both approaches is high, with 99% for the local and 98% for the global

approach. Considering that the evaluation dataset is imbalanced with 3% anomalies, these results are no guarantee for a good predictor. If all wrong classifications are false negatives, only one-third of the anomalies are detected by the global approach and two-thirds by the local approach. Therefore, the next metric to examine is the F1 score. The F1 score shows a different behavior. With 0.6488, the global approach performs significantly worse than the local approach with 0.8971. Further analysis of the detection categories reveals the reason for the different scores. The number of detected anomalies (TP) for the local approach is 8584, almost twice as high as the 4483 for the global approach. This means that the local approach detects significantly more anomalies. This is also reflected in the number of undetected anomalies (FN). The local approach leaves only 154 anomalies undetected, while the global approach leaves 4255 anomalies undetected. This corresponds to 27 times more undetected anomalies for the global approach. The number of falsely detected anomalies (FP) is three times higher for the local approach at 1815 compared with 598 for the global approach. This results in more overhead due to the handling of benign incidents. These results are also reflected in the number of correctly predicted negatives (TN). Figure 3 supports these findings for all included attack types. The local approach achieves high accuracies above 95% and F1 above 0.97 for all attack types. The global approach suffers from the high FN. It only performs well in the generic category with 93% accuracy and 0.9665 F1. This category accounts for

FIGURE 2 | Traffic split: total traffic to device IPs.

TABLE 2 | Performance evaluation.

Approach	Accuracy	F1 score	TP	TN	FP	FN
Local	0.9930	0.8971	8584	269,092	1815	154
Global	0.9826	0.6488	4483	270,311	598	4255

FIGURE 3 | Attack type scores.

TABLE 3 | Shallow model performance.

Approach	Accuracy	F1 score	TP	TN	FP	FN	Time to train
Local	0.9931	0.8991	8648	269,056	1851	90	3480 s
Global	0.9691	0.4710	3852	267,144	3765	4886	15,752 s

36% of all anomalies. For exploits, which make up 25% of the anomalies, it performs poorly with 8% accuracy and 0.1407 F1. For worms, which make up 0.08% of the anomalies, it detects none, while the local approach detects all.

Regarding the question: How does the decentralized approach compare to the centralized approach? The detection performance results show that the local models outperform the global model. In particular, the significant improvement in the detection of true anomalies is a key factor.

4.8.2 | Model Complexity

Table 3 presents the results of EX2. It contains the results for the local and global approaches. The better values are printed in bold. In terms of detection performance, the local approach improves slightly. The accuracy is almost the same, while the F1 score increases by 0.2%. This is due to an increase in the number of detected anomalies. The number of undetected anomalies decreases from 154 to 90. False positives increase slightly from 1815 to 1851. The global approach deteriorates in all categories. In particular, it performs worse in the categories where it outperforms the local approach in EX1. The number of false positives increases from 598 to 3765, which is an increase of 800% and is now twice as high as for the local approach. This results in a 17.8% decrease in F1. The accuracy remains high at 97% with a loss of only 1%, showing the limitations of accuracy as a performance metric. The reduced complexity is reflected in the training time. The training times drop from 21,404 to 15,752s for the global approach and from 4560 to 3480s for the local approach. Figure 5 shows the training times for the default models.

Regarding the question—“How does complexity reduction affect performance for local and global?”—the results point in a clear direction. For the local approach, there is no negative impact on detection performance. On the other hand, there is a significant increase in false positives for the global approach. This shows that only the models of the local approach can be simplified. Compared with the results in Figure 5, the

training times for both approaches are reduced by 25%. This answers the question: How does complexity affect training and processing times?

4.8.3 | Required Data

Figure 4 displays the results of EX3. It shows the accuracy of the global and local models at different levels of input data. The horizontal axis represents the ratio of the 562,045 training samples. The vertical axis represents the score for the accuracies and the F1 scores. Until 40% of the training samples, accuracy and F1 score increase for the local approach. At this point, both values reach a value of more than 99% for the accuracy and 0.9 for the F1 score. From that point on, the values do not change significantly until 100% of the training samples. For the global models, both values reach their final level at 70% of the samples. The accuracy reaches 98%, and the F1 score reaches 0.65.

With that, the question—“What is the training data requirement of both approaches to achieve their final performance?”—can be answered as follows: The results show, that the local approach needs only 40% of the available training samples to reach its final detection performance. In contrast, the global approach needs 70% of the available samples for its final detection performance. This also affects the training time. Figure 5 shows that the training times grow linearly with the number of samples. Taking this information into account, the local approach can be trained in less than half of the original time and 57% of the time needed for the global approach. In the PC environment, the 30% savings between the global and local approaches amounts to 6739 s. Through parallelization, the local approach even saves 13,681 s, which corresponds to a time saving of 63%.

4.8.4 | Training Times

Figure 5 shows the results of the training time measurements for EX4. The horizontal axis shows the ratio of the total 562,045 training set samples. The vertical axis shows the

training time in seconds. The first observation is the linear growth of training time with increasing number of training samples. This is true for all devices. Regarding scalability, this shows a growth of $O(n)$ with increasing training data. The training times of the local and global approaches are a direct comparison of both approaches within the same environment.

FIGURE 4 | Complexity.

FIGURE 5 | Training times.

TABLE 4 | Latency: Local processing.

Environment	Time per sample	Time to process box	Samples to process box	Data to process	Time to train
PI	1.08596 ms	14.65 s	13,493	4.4 MB	25,497 s
PC	0.09363 ms	11.09 s	266,044	65.3 MB	21,404 s

Both measurements use the PC environment. In this direct comparison, it can be seen that the training of the local model is significantly faster, with an advantage between 78% and 80% in time savings. These huge savings are in line with expectations and are mainly due to the parallelization of the decentralized training. In contrast to the centralized approach, the decentralized approach can take advantage of using all available CPU cores. In the PC environment, parallelization allows the use of all 12 available CPU cores and the training of 12 independent models in parallel. With a total number of 43 device models to be trained, the system can process 28% of the models in parallel. Optimal parallelization would require at least 43 CPU cores to train all models in parallel. Because the local datasets are not equal in size, the device with the largest dataset determines the total processing time. This is shown by the *Optimal* curve. It shows the processing time of the largest model in an optimal environment where all models can be processed in parallel. Compared with the partially parallelized decentralized approach in the PC environment, it further reduces the training time by 50%. Compared with the centralized case, the optimal case can reduce the training time by up to 90%. The largest model is also trained in the PI environment for real-world IoT results on constrained hardware. Compared with the centralized training within the PC environment, the training times are only 20% higher.

To answer the question—“How does the training time compare between the two approaches and on constrained versus powerful hardware?”—it can be said that although the PI performs 10 times slower than the optimal case, it can still compete with centralized training. Finally, the local model performs only 20% slower when running on 10 times slower hardware. The benefits in terms of optimization goals clearly outweigh the increase in training and processing time. In addition, the current version 4 of the Raspberry PI is expected to reduce processing by 30%–50%. The comparison of both approaches within the same environment shows a significant reduction in training time for the decentralized approach due to its ability to be parallelized.

4.8.5 | Latency

Table 4 shows the results of the processing latency measurements of EX5. The time per sample shows that the PC processes the data 11.6 times faster than the PI. However, this is only a comparison of raw processing speed and does not reflect real-world behavior. In a real-world scenario, the local device only needs to process its own traffic, while the global predictor needs to process all data within the corresponding timeframe. Instead of taking the entire evaluation data, the box measurements consider only one particular device to be processed. They take the largest device box out of the 279,645 samples to provide

the upper bound for the processing time. The dataset box for IP 59.166.0.2 contains 13,493 samples. To simulate the decentralized approach, the experiment processes these 13,493 samples on the PI. To simulate the global approach, the experiment identifies the chunk of samples that contains all entries for IP 59.166.0.2. This chunk of 266,044 samples contains the traffic from all the other devices transmitting data in the meantime. It is processed on the PC to simulate the processing of the collected data from all the devices. In this real-world experiment, the PC is only 1.32 times faster with processing times of 11.09s for the PC and 14.65s for the PI.

Table 5 shows the results of the theoretical calculation of transmission delay latency. It lists all of the possible network connections for the PI, along with their maximum data transfer rates. The considered dataset box is again for IP 59.166.0.2 containing 13,493 samples. The first calculations of the transmission delay cover the time to transmit all raw data for the device Box to the central instance. The second calculations show the share of the transmission delay toward the local processing of the global model in the PC environment. This highlights how much delay is added when the data are not processed locally. While the difference is negligible at the theoretical maximum of GbE, the delay becomes significant at lower speeds. It can add up to 7.12% of the local latency for the

TABLE 5 | Latency: Internode.

Connectivity	Transfer rate	Transmission delay	
		Box of size 4.4MB	Share of latency
Raspberry Pi 3 B+ (2.4GHz)	46,7Mbit/s	0.790s	7.12%
Raspberry Pi 3 B+ (5GHz)	102Mbit/s	0.362s	3.26%
Raspberry Pi 3 B+ (eth)	300Mbit/s	0.123s	1.11%
Theoretical GbE Max	1Gbit/s	0.037s	0.33%

TABLE 6 | Federated augmentation detection performance.

Approach	Accuracy	F1 score	TP	TN	FP	FN
Federated augmentation	0.9837	0.7926	8685	266,414	4493	53
Training	0.9930	0.8977	8608	269,075	1832	130

TABLE 7 | Bootstrapping time.

Approach	Time till initial model		Model aggregation		Similarity analysis	
	Smallest trainset	Largest trainset	Smallest trainset	Largest trainset	Smallest trainset	Largest trainset
Selective FL	3.8913s	681.8319s	0.3920s	0.4151s	3.3925s	681.4148
Training	42.6145s	26,034.4659s	—	—	—	—

2.4-GHz link. In this case, the PC processing advantage over PI drops from 32% to 23%. It can drop even further because currently only the serialization delay is covered for transmission latency.

Regarding the question—“How is the prediction latency, including introduced latency by slower hardware?”—the latency measurements indicate that the local approach can mitigate the need for high-processing resources. Despite the significantly higher resources required for processing the global approach, it only provides a minor benefit in latency. Edge hardware can even compete in latency with constrained resources. Both measurements indicate that despite the PI’s slower performance per sample, the decentralized approach results in nearly identical total local processing times, with only a 1.32 factor advantage in favor of the PC environment in the real world.

4.8.6 | Federated Augmentation

Table 6 shows the results of EX6. Bold values indicate the model that performs better in each category. For most metrics, the standard training produces better results. In particular, augmentation increases the false positives by 145% from 1832 to 3393. This results in a decrease of the F1 score by 10%. The only metrics where the augmentation provides an improvement are the false negatives and the true positives. For these metrics, the undetected anomalies are 145% higher for the standard training.

Based on these results, the answer to the question—“Can inclusion of selective federated knowledge improve the detection performance?”—is twofold. Regarding accuracy and F1 score, the augmentation did not improve the detection performance. Regarding the undetected anomalies, the augmentation did improve the detection performance. In cases where undetected anomalies are weighted more heavily than false positives, the optimization can be recommended.

4.8.7 | Bootstrapping Time

Table 7 contains the times for model bootstrapping measured in EX7. The time required to train a new model ranges from 42.6s

for the smallest model with only 22 samples to 26034.5s for the largest model with 13,512 samples. The selective FL approach requires only 3.9s to provide an initial model for the smallest model and 681.8s for the largest model. This shows that both approaches depend on the size of the dataset for the new model. Unlike training, the runtime of the selective FL approach also depends on the number of models to be analyzed. In EX7, the number of 43 devices is given by the number of devices contained in the training dataset. A further increase in models results in linear growth of the runtime, as Figure 6 shows. A detailed analysis of the selective FL approach shows that both parts, similarity detection and model aggregation, grow linearly. However, the similarity detection part consumes most of the runtime.

Table 8 shows the detection performance for training and fast bootstrapping. Bold values indicate the model that performs better in each category. The results show that the fast bootstrapping approach almost reaches the detection performance

FIGURE 6 | Scalability.

TABLE 8 | Bootstrapping detection performance.

Approach	Accuracy	F1 score	TP	TN	FP	FN
Fast bootstrapping	0.9918	0.8789	8368	268,972	1935	370
Training	0.9930	0.8977	8608	269,075	1832	130

FIGURE 7 | Fast bootstrapping attack type scores.

of the natively trained model. While the accuracy differs by only 0.12%, the F1 scores differ by almost 2%. Detailed analysis shows that the most significant difference is in false negatives. Fast bootstrapping misses three times as many anomalies with 370 versus 130. The attack type scores for both approaches are shown in Figure 7. Because the differences are that small, the vertical axis starts at 0.8. The analysis of the attack-type scores reveals that the most significant differences occur in the detection of Analysis and Generic anomalies. For both types, the accuracy is 8% worse and the F1 score is 4% worse. The number of training samples can be excluded as a reason for this difference. The Analysis type is one of the smallest anomaly classes with only 44 samples, while Generic is the largest class with 3189 samples. It is worth noting that fast bootstrapping outperforms training for the Fuzzers, DoS, and Exploits classes, albeit by a small margin.

In response to the questions—“Can bootstrapping be accelerated?” and “Is complete aggregation valid?”—it can be concluded that the selective FL approach significantly speeds up the bootstrapping process. For the smallest model, the selective FL approach takes only 9.2% of the training time, and for the largest model, it takes only 2.6%. In terms of detection performance metrics, the fast bootstrapping performs slightly worse. Combining both results, selective FL can be considered a valid option for quickly creating detection models.

5 | Conclusion

This article introduced decentralized anomaly detection using deep feed-forward neural networks. The use of decentralized anomaly detection with local models shows significant improvements over centralized approaches. Section 2 presents related works that provide solutions for single optimization goals. However, it finds no approach for decentralized local AD modeling that fulfills all of them. Section 3 presents the approach of decentralized local AD models. It highlights decentralized placement on devices as a solution to improve latency, bandwidth usage, and privacy. The independence of models provides flexibility in retraining, model addition, and load balancing. The reduced amount of characteristics that need to be learned

in the local case enables the creation of lightweight AD models. Possible problems due to the reduced amount of training data are addressed by using selective FL.

The evaluation results of Section 4 show superior detection performance over a centralized approach. They also demonstrate the simplification of AD models that makes them executable on constrained IoT devices. The local approach leads to the fact that constrained IoT hardware can compensate for a performance gap of a factor of 10. The use of local models also reduces the amount of training data required by 30% compared with the centralized approach. The improvements in detection performance, flexibility, and model complexity support the recommendation to use local models. Even if they are not distributed, they can greatly reduce training times on centralized hardware. For constrained hardware, selective model aggregation allows fast model bootstrapping, reducing the time for an initial model by more than 90%. Possible problems with reduced amounts of training data per model can be compensated by applying selective FL. Current limitations are the use of PyTorch models and the associated resource requirements. The use of TinyML could push the approach even further to the edge, including microcontrollers such as the ESP32. Future work will elaborate on the selection of similarity criteria. Further research will also be invested in local retraining of fast bootstrapped models.

Acknowledgements

Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

1. M. Antonakakis, "Understanding the Mirai Botnet, 26th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 17)," USENIX Association Vancouver, BC, (2017): 1093–1110, <https://www.usenix.org/conference/usenixsecurity17/technical-sessions/presentation/antonakakis>.
2. G. Karatas and O. Sahingoz, "Neural Network Based Intrusion Detection Systems With Different Training Functions," in *2018 6th International Symposium on Digital Forensic and Security (ISDFS)*, (IEEE, 2018), 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISDFS.2018.8355327>.
3. N. Moustafa and J. Slay, "UNSW-NB15: A Comprehensive Data Set for Network Intrusion Detection Systems (UNSW-NB15 Network Data Set)," in *2015 Military Communications and Information Systems Conference (MilCIS)*, (IEEE, 2015), 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MilCIS.2015.7348942>.
4. C. Lübben, M.-O. Pahl, and M. I. Khan, "Using Deep Learning to Replace Domain Knowledge," in *2020 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)*, (IEEE, 2020), 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCC50000.2020.9219567>.
5. T. D. Nguyen, S. Marchal, M. Miettinen, M. H. Dang, N. Asokan, and A. Sadeghi, "Diot: A Crowdsourced Self-Learning Approach for Detecting Compromised IoT Devices," *CoRR abs/1804.07474*, (2018).
6. C. Lübben and M.-O. Pahl, "Advances in ML-Based Anomaly Detection for the IoT," in *2021 5th Cyber Security in Networking Conference (CSNet)*, (IEEE, 2021), 18–22, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSNet52717.2021.9614280>.
7. H. Li, K. Ota, and M. Dong, "Learning IoT in Edge: Deep Learning for the Internet of Things With Edge Computing," *IEEE Network* 32, no. 1 (2018): 96–101.
8. T. Luo and S. G. Nagarajan, "Distributed Anomaly Detection Using Autoencoder Neural Networks in wsn for IoT," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, (IEEE, 2018), 1–6.
9. J. Ren, H. Wang, T. Hou, S. Zheng, and C. Tang, "Federated Learning-Based Computation Offloading Optimization in Edge Computing-Supported Internet of Things," *IEEE Access* 7 (2019): 69194–69201.
10. J. Schneible and A. Lu, "Anomaly Detection on the Edge," in *MILCOM 2017-2017 IEEE Military Communications Conference (MILCOM)*, (IEEE, 2017).
11. S. A. Rahman, H. Tout, C. Talhi, and A. Mourad, "Internet of Things Intrusion Detection: Centralized, On-Device, or Federated Learning?," *IEEE Network* 34, no. 6 (2020): 310–317.
12. G. Thamilarasu and S. Chawla, "Towards Deep-Learning-Driven Intrusion Detection for the Internet of Things," *Sensors* 19 (2019): 1977.
13. D. Kim and M. Gofman, "Comparison of Shallow and Deep Neural Networks for Network Intrusion Detection," in *2018 IEEE 8th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC)*, (IEEE, 2018), 204–208, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCWC.2018.8301755>.
14. S. Hanif, T. Ilyas, and M. Zeeshan, "Intrusion Detection in IoT Using Artificial Neural Networks on UNSW-15 Dataset," in *2019 IEEE 16th International Conference on Smart Cities: Improving Quality of Life Using ICT & IoT and AI (HONET-ICT)*, (IEEE, 2019), 152–156, <https://doi.org/10.1109/HONET.2019.8908122>.
15. N. Moustafa, B. Turnbull, and K. R. Choo, "An Ensemble Intrusion Detection Technique Based on Proposed Statistical Flow Features for Protecting Network Traffic of Internet of Things," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 6, no. 3 (2019): 4815–4830.
16. M. Al-Hawawreh, N. Moustafa, and E. Sitnikova, "Identification of Malicious Activities in Industrial Internet of Things Based on Deep Learning Models," *Journal of Information Security and Applications* 41 (2018): 1–11.
17. A. Telikani and A. Gandomi, "Cost-Sensitive Stacked Auto-Encoders for Intrusion Detection in the Internet of Things," *Internet of Things* 14 (2019): 100122.
18. S. Rezvy, Y. Luo, M. Petridis, A. Lasebae, and T. Zebin, "An Efficient Deep Learning Model for Intrusion Classification and Prediction in 5G and IoT Networks," in *2019 53rd Annual Conference on Information Sciences and Systems (CISS)*, (IEEE, 2019), 1–6.
19. N. Koroniotis, N. Moustafa, E. Sitnikova, and J. Slay, "Towards Developing Network Forensic Mechanism for Botnet Activities in the IoT Based on Machine Learning Techniques," in *Mobile Networks and Management*, eds. J. Hu, I. Khalil, Z. Tari, and S. Wen (Springer International Publishing, 2018), 30–44.
20. D. Lanoë, M. Hurfin, and E. Totel, "A Scalable and Efficient Correlation Engine to Detect Multi-Step Attacks in Distributed Systems," in *2018 IEEE 37th Symposium on Reliable Distributed Systems (SRDS)*, (IEEE, 2018), <https://doi.org/10.1109/SRDS.2018.00014>.
21. Y. Meidan, M. Bohadana, A. Shabtai, et al., "ProfilIoT: A Machine Learning Approach for IoT Device Identification Based on Network Traffic Analysis," in *SAC'17*, (Association for Computing Machinery, 2017).
22. A. Sivanathan, H. H. Gharakheili, F. Loi, et al., "Classifying IoT Devices in Smart Environments Using Network Traffic Characteristics," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing* 18, no. 8 (2019): 1745–1759.

23. M. Miettinen, S. Marchal, I. Hafeez, et al., "IoT Sentinel Demo: Automated Device-Type Identification for Security Enforcement in IoT," in *2017 IEEE 37th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS)*, (IEEE, 2017).
24. M.-O. Pahl and F.-X. Aubet, "All Eyes on You: Distributed Multi-Dimensional IoT Microservice Anomaly Detection," in *2018 14th International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM)*, (IEEE, 2018), 72–80.
25. I. Hafeez, A. Y. Ding, M. Antikainen, and S. Tarkoma, *Real-Time IoT Device Activity Detection in Edge Networks* (Springer, 2018).
26. A. Hamza, D. Ranathunga, H. H. Gharakheili, T. Benson, M. Roughan, and V. Sivaraman, "Verifying and Monitoring IoTs Network Behavior Using MUD Profiles," CoRR abs/1902.02484, (2019), <http://arxiv.org/abs/1902.02484>.
27. N. DeMarinis and R. Fonseca, "Toward Usable Network Traffic Policies for IoT Devices in Consumer Networks," in *Proceedings of the 2017 Workshop on Internet of Things Security and Privacy, IoTS&P'17*, (Association for Computing Machinery, 2017), 43–48, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3139937.3139949>.
28. G. Spathoulas, S. Evangelatos, M. Anagnostopoulos, G. Mema, and S. Katsikas, "Detection of Abnormal Behavior in Smart-Home Environments," in *2019 4th South-East Europe Design Automation, Computer Engineering, Computer Networks and Social Media Conference (SEEDA-CECNSM)*, (IEEE, 2019), 1–6.
29. C. Lübben, S. Schäffner, and M.-O. Pahl, "Continuous Microservice Re-Placement in the IoT," in *NOMS 2022-2022 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium*, (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, 2022), 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS54207.2022.9789780>.
30. C. Lübben and M.-O. Pahl, "Distributed Device-Specific Anomaly Detection Using Deep Feed-Forward Neural Networks," in *NOMS 2023-2023 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium*, (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, 2023), 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS56928.2023.10154360>.
31. C. Lübben and M.-O. Pahl, "Similarity-Based Selective Federated Learning for Distributed Device-Specific Anomaly Detection," in *NOMS 2024-2024 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium*, (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, 2024), 1–9.
32. C. Lübben and M.-O. Pahl, "Distributed Device-Specific Anomaly Detection for Resource-Constrained Devices," in *NOMS 2023-2023 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium*, (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, 2023), 1–3, <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS56928.2023.10154372>.
33. UNSW Sydney, The UNSW-NB15 Dataset (2021), <https://research.unsw.edu.au/projects/unsw-nb15-dataset>.

Biographies

Christian Lübben is a research associate and PhD student at the chair of Network Architectures and Services at Technical University of Munich (TUM). He received his master's degree in Informatics from TUM in May 2018. His main area of interest is in the Internet of Things and Smart Space research. His research focus lies on optimizing IoT smart spaces using Artificial Intelligence (AI) based data analytics. Challenges include security, usability, resilience, scalability, and performance.

Marc-Oliver Pahl is a full professor for cybersecurity at IMT Atlantique, a French Grand École. There he leads the industrial chair Cybersecurity for Critical National Infrastructures (). Marc-Oliver is an adjunct professor at Carleton University in Canada. Marc-Oliver is president of the German chapter of the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) () and member of the executive committee of the German Informatics Society (gi.de). He leads the Future Education activities of the German-French Academy for the Industry of the Future (). Marc-Oliver's research focuses on a holistic approach to cybersecurity with an emphasis on collaborative approaches, including VR-based cybersecurity interfaces and novel side-channel based anomaly detection and federated learning. He is an experienced teacher and an eLearning pioneer who has received several teaching awards. He continuously organizes events for larger audiences, such as the Speaker Series and the future-iot.org PhD School Series.